

Fermat's Principle, Hypothetical Velocity, Lorentz Transformations and a Moving Mirror

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In (1) we showed that Fermat's minimum time approach is equivalent to a hypothetical velocity approach for two rays. This holds for Snell's law, a fixed mirror and a mirror moving at constant velocity v . The hypothetical velocity H forms a hypotenuse and the two rays make angles AA and BB with a normal (y axis). $H\sin(AA) = v(\text{relative } A)$ and $H\sin(BB) = v(\text{relative } B)$ where v relative is the relative velocity in the direction of the ray. For A it is $1-v \cos(AA)$ and for B $1+v \cos(BB)$ for $c=1$.

In (2) the author notes that Fermat's principle yields the same result Einstein obtained in a 1905 paper using Lorentz transformations. In this note, we wish to show how the hypothetical velocity approach (and hence Fermat's principle) is related to Lorentz transformations for a moving mirror.

Moving Mirror

Consider a mirror of length L moving downward in the y direction with constant velocity v . An incident ray makes an angle AA with the normal and the reflected ray BB also with the normal. In (2) Fermat's principle of least time is used to obtain the result:

$$\sin(AA) - \sin(BB) = -v/c \sin(AA+BB) \quad ((1))$$

This equation is compatible with Einstein's 1905 result (as noted in (2)) which yields:

$$\cos(BB) = \{ -2v/c + (1+vv/cc) \cos(AA) \} / \{ 1-2v/c \cos(AA) + vv/cc \} \quad ((3))$$

One may simply use ((3)) and $\sin(BB) = \sqrt{1-\cos(BB)\cos(BB)}$ in ((1)) to see that compatibility is achieved.

The question which arises is why should Fermat's principle yield the same result as Lorentz transformations for a moving mirror? We try to answer this question by linking the hypothetical velocity approach to Fermat's principle and then to Lorentz transformations.

Hypothetical Velocity Approach

In (1) we showed that Fermat's principle for two ray scenarios (including a moving mirror) is equivalent to a hypothetical velocity approach where the hypothetical velocity H is along the x axis with the mirror moving down in the y direction and acts as a hypotenuse. Thus:

$$H \sin(AA) = v(\text{relative } a) \quad \text{and} \quad H \sin(BB) = v(\text{relative } b) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Here } v(\text{relative } a) = c - v \cos(AA) \quad \text{and} \quad v(\text{relative } b) = c + v \cos(BB) \quad ((5))$$

In other words the relative velocities are along the ray directions.

((4)) then leads to the fundamental result ((1)) obtained using Fermat's minimization of time.

We let $c=1$ going forward. The goal is then to link the hypothetical velocity approach to Lorentz transformations. To do so we note that the incident ray hits the mirror at x and the reflected ray travels such that its x projection is $L-x$.

The link with the relative velocities ((5)) and Lorentz transformations is the following:

The relative velocities divided by t_a or t_b are the same as the time intervals in the moving frame as given by a Lorentz transformation ((6))

In particular one may note that the incident ray travels a time t_a to the mirror and the reflected ray a time t_b . The objective is to keep x and $L-x$ in the moving frame because these distances are perpendicular to motion, but to calculate the new time intervals Δt_a and Δt_b .

We use the Lorentz transformation:

$$\begin{vmatrix} \gamma & \gamma v \\ \gamma v & \gamma \end{vmatrix}$$

For t_a consider the initial time $t=0$ and a position y on the y axis. Then in the moving frame:

$$t_0' = \gamma v y$$

For the final time $t = t_a$ and $y=0$, t' final $= \gamma t_a$

$$\Delta t' \text{ (in the moving frame) is } \gamma (t_a - v y) \text{ for A } ((7))$$

For the reflected ray it is easier to consider $t=0$ and $y=0$ as the initial point. These are the same in the moving frame. The final time is:

$$v y + t_b \text{ where } y \text{ is the same as for A in the lab frame.}$$

Finally one sets the horizontal velocity in the moving frame to be equal:

$$(L-x) / (v y + t_b) = x / (t_a - v y) \quad ((8))$$

Now $(L-x)/t_b = \sin(BB)$ and $x/t_a = \sin(AA)$ and $(-v y/t_b + 1) = (v \cos(BB) + 1)$ and $(1-v y/t_a) = (1-v \cos(AA))$. These time intervals are equivalent to the relative velocities used in the hypothetical velocity approach. In the hypothetical velocity approach:

$$H \sin(AA) = H x/t_a = v(\text{relative a})/t_a = \text{Lorentz } \Delta t_a' \text{ (in the moving frame) } ((9a)) \text{ and}$$

$$H \sin(BB) = H (L-x) / t_b = v(\text{relative b}) / t_b = \text{Lorentz } \Delta t_b' \text{ (in the moving frame) } ((9b))$$

Where $v(\text{relative a}) = 1 - v \cos(AA)$ and $v(\text{relative b}) = 1 + v \cos(BB)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion we have shown in (1) that a Fermat's minimum time approach is equivalent to a hypothetical velocity approach (with H the hypothetical velocity lying along the x axis and acting as an hypotenuse to the incident and reflected rays for a mirror moving downward in the y direction with constant velocity v) such that:

$$H \sin(AA) = v(\text{relative a}) \quad \text{and} \quad H \sin(BB) = v(\text{relative b})$$

$v(\text{relative a}) = 1 - v \cos(AA)$ and $v(\text{relative b}) = 1 + v \cos(BB)$ i.e. the relative velocities are along the ray directions.

$\sin(AA) = x / t_a$ and $\sin(BB) = (L-x) / t_b$ so one may consider x and L-x as horizontal distances unchanged by a Lorentz transformation. We show that $v(\text{relative a})$ and $v(\text{relative b})$ divided by t_a and t_b respectively are the time intervals in the moving frame. Thus the hypothetical velocity approach maps directly to Lorentz transformations. In other words, Fermat's minimum time approach, the hypothetical velocity approach and Lorentz transformations are all equivalent.

References

- 1 Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Equivalence of Fermat's Least Time with a Hypothetical Velocity (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
2. Gjurchinovski, A. Einstein's Mirror and Fermat's Principle of least time (Am. J. of Phys 72 (10) Oct. 2004)
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